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Evelyn's Sense of Meaninglessness in Her Existential Despair in *Everything Everywhere All at Once* Movie Script

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Abstract

This article examines how the movie script Everything Everywhere All at Once by Daniel Kwan and Daniel Scheinert portrays one of the characteristics of existential despair: a sense of meaninglessness. A sense of meaninglessness is a situation when an individual is at a loss of meaning or feels there is no point in their existence. The movie tells the journey of Evelyn Wang, who feels helpless as she struggles to maintain her relationships, particularly with her husband and daughter, while also facing overwhelming responsibilities in her daily life. Through the lens of Søren Kierkegaard's existential despair theory, this study analyzes how Evelyn's experience reflects the crisis of meaning and self-identity. The research explores how her journey across multiple realities serves as a metaphor for her search for purpose and self-acceptance, ultimately questioning whether true meaning can be found amidst chaos. By applying an existentialist framework, this article aims to provide deeper insight into how Everything Everywhere All at Once illustrates the modern struggle with meaning, identity, and personal agency.

Keywords: Daniel Kwan, Daniel Scheiner, *Everything Everywhere All at Once*, Existential Despair, Sense of Meaninglessness

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INTRODUCTION

Literature works are a reflection of the real world, and movies have been one of the literary works that reflect everyday aspects of human life including existential despair. According to Kierkegaard, existential despair is a social phenomenon that happens throughout humans' lives when they feel concerned about their existential condition (Taghizadeh, 2023; Roy & bin Che, 2023) They feel discomfort, fear, and/or anxiety regarding the meaning or the value of their life (Farr, 2021; Shanthi & Gonsalves, 2021).

One of the characteristics of existential despair is a sense of meaninglessness. Individuals who are in despair are seen to have lost their meaning and contrary to that, to be a human is to strive infinitely. Therefore, having nothing to strive for causing them to have a sense of meaninglessness (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). A sense of meaninglessness can be caused when individuals are constantly questioning or searching for the meaning of their life yet they fail to do so (Nzengu et al, 2021).

The movie *Everything Everywhere All at Once* by Daniel Kwan and Daniel Scheinert, published on June 22, 2022, is an action sci-fi movie that has caught the eye of everyone for its innovative narrative structure, visual storytelling, and profound thematic depth. The researchers want to examine how the character Evelyn in *Everything Everywhere All at Once* illustrates the concepts of sense of meaninglessness of existential despair, as proposed by Søren Kierkegaard.

The movie follows the story of Evelyn Wang, a Chinese-American immigrant who has to take care of her job and her family on the other side. Therefore, Evelyn's life is a relentless cycle of obligations, disappointments, and unfulfilled expectations that leads her to existential despair. Evelyn is forced to confront the weight of her existence. Crushed by the absurdity of it all, she is on the edge of existential despair, tempted to surrender (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Evelyn then gets drawn into a multi-dimensional adventure where she has to communicate with parallel-universe versions of herself in order to stop a villain called Jobu Tupaki. Throughout the film, Evelyn is regularly forced to make tough decisions. She often questions her ability to overcome Jobu

Tupaki and get her child back without losing herself in the process (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). Finding solace in the very absurd life is what she is after.

The researchers choose this movie and theory for their analysis because a sense of meaninglessness is a common thing yet quite hard to overcome (Hanson, 2021). However, it is critical for humans to overcome it, in order to be authentic. Living authentically involves making choices that are true to one's own values, beliefs, and experiences, rather than conforming to external expectations or societal norms (Kierkegaard, 2009).

Thus, the researchers analyze how the character Evelyn portrays a sense of meaninglessness throughout the storyline of the movie, and how this affects her relationship and her personal growth. Therefore, the researchers use examples from the movie script by taking dialogues, gestures, and narrations, to illustrate the challenges of having a sense of meaninglessness and how she manages to solve it.

METHOD

This research is employed through a qualitative method that examines certain concepts and textual data. The researchers try to analyze how the character Evelyn in *Everything Everywhere All at Once* illustrates a sense of meaninglessness concept in existential despair, by focusing the research on Evelyn's journey, of navigating a fractured relationship with her family while also maintaining her responsibilities. This research aims to find out how a sense of meaninglessness is portrayed by the main character using a sense of meaninglessness concept in existential despair. By taking a close reading of the entire movie script and the dialogues between the main characters. It also provides quotations from the movie script and the sources that support the analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Evelyn's Existential Despair in *Everything Everywhere All at Once*

Daniel Kwan & Daniel Scheinert's movie tells about Evelyn Quan Wang who experiences existential despair. Evelyn's existential despair is portrayed in the movie with a sense of meaninglessness. She feels helpless to deal with everyday never-ending chores and maintaining a good relationship with her family even if they have different values. However, she tries to overcome her feeling of despair through her journey of finding meaning. The proof of Evelyn's sense of meaninglessness is stated in the quotation as follows:

Data 1

...She looks around the room. She doesn't see much to be proud of. (Act 2)

Evelyn wants to make her father proud and make sure that everything seems perfect in her father's eyes. However, she does not feel like anything could be worth seeing by his father. She feels nothing in her home and life could make her father proud. Ever since she was a child, she has felt that she has always been a disappointment to her father (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). Oftentimes her choices in life have made her father question her. It does not make it any better, she is just an owner of a mediocre laundromat with her husband, Waymond, whom she chooses to marry when she is still a teenager.

Data 2

"My mom is gonna be EXTRA caring now that Gong Gong's here..." (Act 3)

Evelyn feels that her father's opinion matters so much that she wants to take care of everything, including her daughter and her choices. She wants to make sure that everything is up to her father's expectations. She knows that she is not the perfect daughter that her father asks for (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). Therefore, she tries her best to make it up to her father by guiding her daughter, Joy, as to 31 what she thinks would make her father pleased and proud. Although, sometimes what they think is best for Joy does not align with Joy's.

Data 3

"I'm sorry it's a girl." (Act 14, Scene 1)

Evelyn is shown a glimpse of when she was born. Her father looks displeased knowing that the newborn baby is a girl. He is hoping that it will be a boy. The memory from the past that is shown to her just confirms her doubts about her existence which is not even wanted in the first place. She

knows from then, that she is going to be a disappointment to her father and it is going to be hard to please him (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). Whatever she does seem cannot satisfy her father and is not up to his standard. Doing anything just seems wrong in her father's eyes even when she is just a child.

Data 4

The camera/Evelyn looks up at a disapproving Gong Gong and then down at her own two sticks... (Act 14, Scene 2)

Then the memories move to when she is still a kid in an elementary school. She is playing but once again there is a look of disappointment on her father's face showing that he disapproves of her action even if she is just playing. Her father thinks that a lady should not act the way she is, running around like a boy. She is born as a girl and she should act like it, the way society already defines how a girl should act (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). Her father expects her to act like the other girls or the society's standards for girls. She should act and speak femininely, not rough and "playful" because that's what boys do.

Data 5

"Ba...It's me again. Wondering when you'll call back..." (Act 14, Scene 8)

Later on, even after choosing Waymond over her family, Evelyn feels a little bit at a lost and hopes that her father can forgive her and call back. She always thinks that her father's opinion matters so much that it has helped her in her life. She feels dependent on him. She is still her father's daughter after all, she grows up knowing her father only wants the best for her (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). She loves Waymond but she also loves her father, she knows and loves him ever since she was a child. Her father taught her a lot of things. She does not regret ever choosing and marrying Waymond, she just wishes that she could still be her father's daughter and feel his love once again.

Data 6

Evelyn is now standing outside of her laundromat with a few suitcases and Gong Gong sitting in a wheelchair, looking clearly disappointed. (Act 14, Scene 15)

After some years of no contact, her father finally comes around and moves in with her. However, he still does not seem too happy with his daughter's choices in life. He thinks that she can do much better than this. He thinks her life could turn out better if she just follows what he orders back then. He thinks it is ridiculous how she chooses Waymond over her family just to go to America and own a laundromat business (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). She could probably have had a more successful life if she had not fallen for Waymond and decided to follow him. However, this will happen because her father is going to live with her from then and she is still his daughter even if she has disappointed him many times.

Data 7

"An evil omniversal being with unimaginable power..." (Act 26)

Alpha Waymond answers Evelyn's question. He sees that every Evelyn from the other universe dies in any kind of way. She is curious as to who in the world wants to kill her. Alpha Waymond explains that it is an evil, omniversal being, with unimaginable power. The name is Jobu Tupaki. Evelyn is baffled because why in the world does anyone want to kill her, and what makes someone have so much hatred towards her. She prefers that Alpha Waymond ask Evelyn from his universe rather than her (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). She feels that her life is already messy enough and now he tells her that someone wants to kill her, making it worse.

Data 8

"...You've been feeling it too, haven't you? Something is off. Your clothes never wear as well the next day, your hair never falls in quite the same way, even your coffee tastes...wrong." (Act 27)

The conversation continues, Alpha Waymond explains that it is not that easy. He says Jobu has been building something and it might have an effect on everyone, and he is sure that Evelyn has been feeling it too. It affects her in her daily life such as her clothes are not comfortable when being worn the next day. Her hair never falls in quite the same way, even the taste of her coffee is just off. She feels it even if she does not notice it. That shows how much of an impact Jobu's existence has on the others around her. If Evelyn does not stop Jobu, her life will change in the future (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 9

“...It was beautiful. I should have listened to Baba. All of those years ago—” (Act 49)

She continues by saying that her life without him is beautiful. She should have listened to her father back then. She regrets it and she should have not followed and married Waymond. She is shown through the verse-jumping that she could have a better life or career. Without Waymond, she could be popular and admired by everyone instead of just being a laundromat owner. Her life would be much more enjoyable than her current life, she is busy taking care of her receipts and such things. Waymond might also have a better life, he could be happier without Evelyn (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 10

Evelyn’s brain is broken. What did her daughter just do? (Act 58)

Joy does not listen to what Evelyn says. She does the opposite of what she is ordered to. Joy starts to fight the officers weirdly and Evelyn could not believe her eyes. This is not the Joy that she knows. She does not teach her to act like that. Her daughter should not be acting this way, especially in an Asian household the younger one always respects the oldest. Evelyn is in shock and also intrigued by what makes Joy become this way. How does she pop his head as if it is a confetti, this is such a bizarre thing for her. Everything does not add up, everything does not make any sense (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 11

“The ‘Great Evil’ that Waymond was talking about...is in my Joy?” (Act 58)

Evelyn then realizes that the Jobu Tupaki whom Alpha Waymond refers to is her daughter. However, she still does not want to believe that the “Great Evil” Alpha Waymond talks about is Joy. It is unbelievable for her, her sweet child, Joy, is the same person who wants to kill her and destroy her universe. Evelyn thinks that there is no way that Joy could be the same person with Jobu Tupaki. However, it is indeed weird with the way she acts with the police officers just now. But it still does not explain how the Joy that she knows is Jobu Tupaki (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 12

“It’s you, it’s been you this whole time. You are the reason my daughter doesn’t call anymore. Why she dropped out of college, gets tattoos. You are why she thinks she’s a gay.” (Act 60)

Evelyn confronts Joy and she feels that she finally figures it all out. She finally understands why Joy does not call anymore, why Joy drops out of school, why Joy gets tattoos, and she also thinks Jobu Tupaki is the reason why her daughter is gay. Because for Evelyn, her daughter will not act like this. She does not wish her daughter to act this way. It is not up to her moral standards. Being gay is also still seen as taboo, especially in Asian households, she is taught that way and she believes that is what her father would like for her to teach her child (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). It is just outrageous the way Joy behaves as if Evelyn and Waymond did not teach her at all.

Data 13

Alpha Gong Gong scoffs at this idea. (Act 69)

Alpha Waymond is still trying to convince both Evelyn and Alpha Gong Gong that Evelyn can and has to defeat Jobu. However, once again, Alpha Gong Gong thinks that it is ridiculous. He thinks that Evelyn is not ready for this, even if her mind could be shattered because she has to maintain herself in this universe and other universes. Jobu is also a strong enemy that Evelyn cannot underestimate. After all, she is the one who brings her into this madness. They are the same level of craziness. Evelyn must have a strong will in order to defeat Jobu. If she is not strong enough, she will be defeated and become like her (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 14

“... There is no way I’m the Evelyn you are looking for.” (Act 69)

Evelyn herself is also doubtful whether she is the right one to defeat Jobu. She thinks she is not up to the standard, just like what Gong Gong thinks of her. She does not think she is the right Evelyn that Alpha Waymond tries to find. After all, she believes what her father says about her has always been right. She has always been a disappointment; she is not strong enough. She is afraid that it will be too late for them to realize that she is not the one who is going to save her. Before that happens, she finally admits that she thinks she is not the right one to defeat Jobu (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 15

“See what? I’m not good at anything.” (Act 69)

Alpha Waymond disagrees. He says that he has seen it clearly and is sure that this is the right Evelyn. He is sure that she can defeat and stop Jobu. However, Evelyn does not believe that. She believes that she is not good at anything. She is good at not being good. Alpha Waymond insists that he has seen something in this version of Evelyn that he cannot see in another Evelyn. Evelyn is baffled, by what kind of things Alpha Waymond sees when the only thing that is clear to her is that she is incompetent and poor at everything she does. Whatever Alpha Waymond sees in her does not change the fact that she is no good at anything (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 16

“What good is all of that power if her mind is already succumbing to the chaos.” (Act 69)

Alpha Waymond does not stop to try to convince Evelyn. He explains that he has seen thousands of Evelyn but none is like her. She has so many goals and dreams that she never achieves and finishes. Every failure branches off into success for another Evelyn in the other universes. However, she is here capable of anything because she is bad at everything. Alpha Gong Gong thinks it is such a waste, because what is good from all of that potential and power if her mind is in chaos. In the end, that potential and power will go to waste because she cannot maintain her sanity (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). If she goes insane, she will not be able to control her power which will be a big disadvantage for her and could be her weakness.

Data 17

“You are already under her spell.” (Act 71, Scene 1)

Continuing from before, Evelyn does not kill Joy. She ends up cutting the duct tape to release Joy. Alpha Gong Gong thinks that Evelyn is under Jobu’s spell. It is confusing why she would choose to let her go rather than kill her while she is in such a weak state. He thinks his daughter should not do that. At least he thinks his Evelyn would not do such a foolish thing to give the enemy a chance. However, it seems that his judgment is wrong because clearly Evelyn is blinded by love for her daughter (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). She still thinks that she can save her daughter, which Alpha Gong Gong thinks is absurd.

Data 18

“Maybe if I become like her, I can save my daughter...” (Act 71, Scene 1)

Evelyn does not have the heart to kill her daughter. She would rather save her and she starts to think that maybe the only way is to become like her daughter. She is willing to fight for her daughter even if she is guilty of her father, but this is something that she has to do. She feels guilty because once again she might disappoint her father but her priority now is her daughter. She wants to do everything she can in order to bring back her daughter, if that even means she has to fight her father if that even means she has to become like her and might lose herself in the process (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

Data 19

“It’s her. She has your soul in her hands. I think the only way I can defeat her...is to become like her.” (Act 76)

Alpha Gong Gong calls the troops from the other universes to stop Evelyn from saving Jobu. Waymond, Evelyn, and Joy are being cornered. Evelyn says to Joy that she understands her struggle and she knows that something has been making her feel sad. Evelyn confidently says that it is because of Jobu that Joy feels that way. The only thing that can defeat Jobu is to become like her and she is certain that she will save her daughter (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022). She reassures Joy that she understands Joy’s struggle and she will help her go through it. After all, she is her mother, she will not let Joy go through it alone.

Data 20

“I said shut up. You don’t matter. This doesn’t matter.” (Act 93, Scene 5)

Evelyn and Joy both stand on their opinion. Evelyn wants to go back with her daughter and live a happy life with her family. Joy wishes her good luck while opening up the bagel for her to see. She starts to get sucked into the bagel. Going back to her current universe, she starts to understand what Joy meant when she says “Nothing matters.” Deirdre comes to her laundromat, bringing some police officers. This is the consequence of Evelyn’s choice. She does not submit her receipts on time.

However, when Deirdre starts screaming for the police to arrest Evelyn, Evelyn is busy with her mind as she mutters that nothing matters (Kwan & Scheinert, 2022).

The Significance of Idea behind Existential Despair and a Sense of Meaninglessness

Despair is not merely a fear of specific external threats but a profound inner chaos that emerges from the awareness of one's freedom and the responsibility to make meaningful choices in life (Kierkegaard, 1980). Failing to make a meaningful decision leads people to start to question themselves whether they have the right purpose or meaning which causes a sense of meaninglessness (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021).

A sense of meaninglessness is a situation when someone feels they have lost their purpose and thinks there is no point in their existence (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). People who experience a sense of meaninglessness have a hard time navigating their life since they do not have a certain goal or purpose to pursue. A sense of meaninglessness can be caused because individuals constantly question the purpose of their life (Kierkegaard, 1980).

Without a clear sense of purpose, individuals may experience emptiness, and this state is not merely a fleeting emotion but a persistent and consuming experience that shapes one's perception of reality (Nzengu et al, 2021). Thus, the inability to find meaning can lead to apathy, where life's experiences seem devoid of value, or even nihilism, where one rejects the possibility of meaning altogether (Nielsen, 2018).

Individuals who have no sense of meaning find it hard to commit to particular beliefs or goals. However, they should confront the overwhelming responsibility of defining their own purpose to reach their fullest potential and authentic self. Therefore, there is a concept of a "leap of faith" where individuals have to embrace meaning despite its inherent uncertainty (Nzengu et al, 2021).

Evelyn's Sense of Meaninglessness in *Everything Everywhere All at Once*

This section discusses how Evelyn's sense of meaninglessness in *Everything Everywhere All at Once* reveals factors that indicate existential despair. These aspects are further explained as follows:

In **Data 1**, Evelyn's action illustrates a sense of meaninglessness because she feels doubtful of her purpose in life (Kierkegaard, 2009). She feels nothing in her home that she could be proud of. Especially to her father, all her life she feels nothing but disappointment. There is no point in her existence, if she does not have any achievement or anything to be proud of. She feels that she never wins in life. This emphasizes that Evelyn is having a hard time finding meaning in her life.

In **Data 2**, Evelyn shows a sign of meaninglessness. She always wants to make sure that everything is up to her father's standards to please him. She wants her father to know and validate her for finally making the right choice. Her father's opinion matters so much that it defines her as a person (Kierkegaard, 1980). Without his validation and affirmation, she feels at a loss and perplexed about her existence. His judgment has helped her to form and build herself. This point emphasizes that his father has a big part in helping her find her meaning in life.

In **Data 3**, Evelyn experiences a sense of meaninglessness because her existence has been questioned by her father ever since she was just a baby (Kierkegaard, 1980). She is not wanted because her father expects to have a baby boy rather than a girl which might be good for nothing. A baby girl is seen as meaningless because a lot of families want a baby boy to help them out in the future. Later, her father's displeased feeling against her underlines her sense of being meaningless before his father's eyes.

In **Data 4**, Evelyn's action shows a sense of meaninglessness. Gong Gong has always been disapproving of Evelyn's actions. It does not matter if she is a child or if she is just playing. She should have been more behaved as a child. Gong Gong thinks if she is destined to be a girl then she should act like it. This builds up Evelyn's confidence to be low because she always thinks that her purpose in life is just to please her father or people in general. Therefore, she experiences a loss of meaning because her existence keeps being judged and questioned by the people around her (Kierkegaard, 1980).

In **Data 5**, Evelyn's action indicates a sense of meaninglessness because her purpose revolves around her father's judgment. It is shown how even after chasing her happiness with Waymond, she

still tries to find her purpose in her father. She feels confused because she does not know where to put herself in her life (Kierkegaard, 1980). Her father's judgment is always better to guide her and define herself in life. She feels afraid that without her father, she has no purpose or goal in life (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). If she behaves beyond her father's values, she will face such meaninglessness in her life, and this happens repeatedly in her life.

In **Data 6**, Evelyn's action indicates a sense of meaninglessness because the first thing that she notices is Gong Gong's displeased face. Even after not meeting for so long, Evelyn realizes that she still could not make her father proud. This makes her question herself again, whether she has made the right path in her life. She feels worthless, since there is nothing that can make her father approve of her existence as an individual (Kierkegaard, 1980). The point highlights how Evelyn puts her father as the biggest judgment to define her worth. Without his father's validation, she experiences a sense of meaninglessness (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021).

In **Data 7**, Evelyn experiences a sense of meaninglessness. She feels more baffled knowing someone with unimaginable power wants to fight her. Her life in her universe is already in chaos and chaos. Now that she knows that herself in another universe is also a disaster, she feels worthless. She feels that she has no purpose at all to fight this villain. She is even doubtful whether she has a purpose at all (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021).

In **Data 8**, Evelyn's action indicates a sense of meaninglessness. The way things are slightly starts to change but she does not notice it because she is way past it. She feels meaningless to care about things that are changing around her (Kierkegaard, 1980). She does not try to stop it when normally it would bother her, but she just ignores it because she already has a sense of meaninglessness. Even when it affects her daily life, she just keeps on going as if it does not influence her.

In **Data 9**, Evelyn's action illustrates meaninglessness because she feels that her father is always right, once again. She feels she has chosen the wrong path in life and it makes her feel worthless (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). The fact that she could have had a better life if she just listened to her father back then makes her feel meaningless. She regrets ever choosing Waymond over her father when this is the outcome. She would not be in these states if she just did what her father ordered.

In **Data 10**, Evelyn's action portrays a sense of meaninglessness when she realizes that her daughter acts rebellious to the officer, she feels that she has failed as a mother. She thinks she has done so much to teach Joy but turns out she has failed and it makes her lose her meaning as a mother (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). She questions herself whether she has done a great job guiding and teaching Joy. The Joy that she knows is not like this or maybe it is just her expectations. She feels meaningless when the reality is not as she expected.

In **Data 11**, Evelyn's sense of meaninglessness can be seen when she finds out that the villain who hunts her is her own daughter. She feels at a lost, to have an enemy and it is her own flesh and blood. She feels disappointed in Joy for turning out this way and herself for failing to be a good mother (Kierkegaard, 1980). A sense of meaninglessness rushes over her and it makes her question her purpose (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). However, she still does not want to believe that the evil villain is her daughter because she expects so much better in herself and her daughter.

In **Data 12**, Evelyn's action indicates a sense of meaninglessness. When she finds out that Jobu Tupaki is her daughter, Joy. She is baffled and lost at words and meanings (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). However, she tries to blame it on Jobu for the way her daughter misbehaves. Because it is not up to her values and standards. However, she feels that it finally makes sense to have something or reason for her daughter's actions. She feels that this could help her ease her meaninglessness to have a reason or something to blame.

In **Data 13**, Evelyn's sense of meaningless can be seen in the way Alpha Gong Gong disagrees with Alpha Waymond's idea. Even in the other universe, her father also disapproves of her, she is not trusted enough to be in charge of something. She is always doubted by her father and it makes her feel meaningless (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021). Her father's judgment caused and affected her sense of meaning. It makes her feel she is not important or strong enough for people to trust her.

In **Data 14**, Evelyn's action illustrates a sense of meaninglessness. People doubt her all the time, even her father. It makes her lose herself. She does not even trust herself to be able to defeat Jobu. She remembers that she is good for nothing, she has no achievement in her life, and never even makes her father proud (Kierkegaard, 1980). Those thoughts get to her and eat up her confidence, making her question her meaning. If she cannot even do anything in her life, how come she could defeat Jobu. She feels meaningless to be in this situation.

In **Data 15**, Evelyn's sense of meaninglessness can be seen when Alpha Waymond tries to convince Evelyn but she convinces herself that she is not good at anything. She is way past the fact that she is no good daughter, mother, and person. She loses her meaning already to believe Alpha Waymond. One person who believes in her does not mean anything when all her life she has always been a failure and no one has believed in her. She feels meaningless and she cannot do anything about it (Kierkegaard, 1980).

In **Data 16**, Evelyn's action indicates she experiences a sense of meaninglessness. Alpha Gong Gong disapproves once again, doubtful whether Evelyn could defeat Jobu and be sane at the same time. Evelyn thinks that Alpha Gong Gong might be right because she is not good at anything and barely keeps herself sane in her universe. She has no trust in herself and loses her purpose because of Alpha Gong Gong's words. Alpha Waymond could be right about her having power and potential, but to her, her father is right because her self-worth is built upon his words. Therefore, she feels meaningless because her father believes that she cannot do it (Kierkegaard, 1980).

In **Data 17**, Evelyn's action illustrates a sense of meaninglessness because her father thinks that Evelyn is in alliance with Jobu. He thinks that Jobu tricks Evelyn's mind and Evelyn is under her spell, which is what makes her act rebellious. She is her mother after all, and that is why Joy is acting like her. Her action makes her father displeased because it is not up to his value. The way she forgives her daughter and defends her says that she chooses a side and it is not with him. Evelyn feels meaningless because her father thinks she is betraying him and allowing her daughter to act like that (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021).

In **Data 18**, Evelyn's sense of meaninglessness can be seen when she thinks the only way to save her child is to become like her. She is willing to change herself to be the person that she thinks is not up to her values and standards (Kierkegaard, 1980). That shows how desperate she is as she feels meaningless without her child. She does not want to lose her daughter even if that means she could lose herself. She feels meaningless because she thinks this is the only way and there is no other option (Kierkegaard in Mulenga, 2021).

In **Data 19**, Evelyn's sense of meaninglessness can be seen is within Evelyn because she has convinced herself that the reason her daughter became like this is because of Jobu. She just feels better about having something to be the reason and to be blamed for the misbehaved actions that her daughters do. She feels meaningless because she believes her daughter is not like this if it is not because of Jobu. She does not want to believe that this is the Joy that she knows (Kierkegaard, 1980).

In **Data 20**, Evelyn's action illustrates a sense of meaninglessness because she finally feels fed up with everything. She has enough and she finds that nothing matters anymore. She does not care anymore about her responsibility as a daughter, mother, and an individual. She feels meaningless doing everything because in the end she always fails. She cannot meet everyone, even her expectations. She loses her purpose because she keeps trying to do everything out of her capability (Kierkegaard, 1980).

CONCLUSION

Everything Everywhere All at Once is a movie by Daniel Kwan and Daniel Scheinert that explores meaninglessness and the overwhelming nature of infinite possibilities. Evelyn Wang, the main character of the movie is a struggling laundromat owner who is suddenly thrust into the multiverse, where she experiences countless alternate versions of herself and she has to find her true purpose while maintaining her responsibility to her family. As she starts to have a sense of meaninglessness, it later contributes to Evelyn's feeling of despair.

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